

Figure S2-A. Frequency distribution of the abundance of focal coral taxa as encountered in our study reef system.

Figure S2-B. Frequency distribution of the abundance of coral competitors as encountered in our study reef system.

Figure S2-C. Boxplot illustrating variability in the size of focal corals as encountered in our study reef system.

Figure S2-D. Boxplot illustrating variability in the size of coral competitors as encountered in our study reef system.

Figure S2-E. Scatterplot illustrating the distribution of focal corals across the coast-to-ocean spatial gradient in our study reef system.

Figure S2-F. Scatterplot illustrating the distribution of coral competitors across the coast-to-ocean spatial gradient in our study reef system.

Figure S2-G. Scatterplot illustrating the distribution in absolute coral net overreach performance across the coast-to-ocean spatial gradient in our study reef system.

Figure S2-H. Scatterplot illustrating the distribution in absolute coral net overgrowth performance across the coast-to-ocean spatial gradient in our study reef system.

